

Why and How?

After your registration, we will get in contact with you to discuss your interests, needs and anticipated involvement to ensure targeted communication with the MICROBE Community members. Our goal is to define relevant services for the MICROBE Community and to inform about project results in a targeted way.

We promise quality and not quantity in informing about MICROBE.

Contact us

Tanja Kostic tanja.kostic@ait.ac.at
Andreas Moser moser@rtd-services.com

MICROBE

the Microbiome
Biobanking (RI)
Enabler

Let us pave the way for
microbiome biobanking

HELMHOLTZ MUNICH

rtd services
innovation | cooperation | inspiration

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No. 101094353.

MICROBE wants to engage and exchange with different stakeholders in the field of microbiome science and relevant research infrastructures. MICROBE aims to set up a network of microbiome scientists (from academia and industry), infrastructure and collection managers, policy- and decision-makers, as well as standardisation and regulatory experts. The strength of the MICROBE Consortium and the wider community is based on multiple skills and expertise acquired while working on microbial resources from different ecosystems (soil, seed, marine and human).

What are our goals?

MICROBE Consortium has set out to tackle one of the big remaining challenges in microbiome research and deliver innovative and validated technological approaches that will enable:

- maximal preservation of taxonomic and functional biodiversity in selected microbiome samples;
- optimal collection and preservation of microbiome samples for defined subsequent analyses;
- targeted isolation of microbiome members from different domains and assembly of synthetic consortia that retain (and even optimise) the functional diversity of original microbiomes.

MICROBE will provide a comprehensive operational blueprint for the establishment of microbiome biobanking infrastructures, including technological requirements, methodological workflows, data pipelines, standards, legal and ethical guidelines, training plans and business opportunities.

To ensure our activities address the needs of the microbiome R&D community and our results are fit-for-use and taken up, a MICROBE Community will be formed, accompanying and advising us on our journey.

Who should join the MICROBE Community?

We aim to set up an international and multidisciplinary MICROBE Community and thus invite:

- individuals and organisations with expertise in microbiome R&D, bioinformatics, biobanking, and related standardisation and regulatory issues,
- research infrastructures representatives,
- business and company managers,
- policy- and decision-makers.

What's in it for you?

We aim to give everyone working in the field of microbiome R&D easy access to state-of-the-art knowledge and a highly professional international community. MICROBE Community members will be able to:

- connect with experts in the field of microbiome science, biobanking technology, bioinformatics and data management, standardisation and regulatory/legal issues;
- learn from and cooperate with others;
- exchange ideas on common challenges and opportunities;
- get informed on the MICROBE results and approaches;
- get informed about relevant events, workshops and initiatives;
- get inspired for new projects and find project partners.

Please, register here to our MICROBE Community:
www.microbeproject.eu/kontakt/

